

Nonlocal electrodynamics of helical metals

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Abstract—We consider the phenomenon of natural optical activity, and related chiral magnetic effect in helical metals, broadly defined as the ones with spin-momentum locking. To reveal the correspondence between the two phenomena, we compute the optical conductivity of a noncentrosymmetric semimetal to linear order in the wave vector of the light wave, specializing to the low-frequency regime. We show that it is the orbital magnetic moment of quasiparticles that is responsible for the natural optical activity, and thus the chiral magnetic effect. We further extend the treatment to the case of spatially non-uniform systems, and derive the most general microscopic formulae for the gyrotropic tensor that satisfies general Onsager relations.

I. INTRODUCTION

Weyl semimetal phase represents a minimal departure from the concept of a topological insulator, in which the requirement of an (ideally) full gap in the Brillouin zone is relaxed to allow an even number of band degeneracies with broken spin-rotation symmetry. The result is an example of a gapless topological phase. [1] In this paper we will use the term “Weyl semimetal” to refer to both Weyl semimetals in the aforementioned narrow sense, as well as symmetry-protected Dirac semimetals, like Na_3Bi and Cd_3As_2 . (See Ref. [2] and references therein.)

One of immediate problems with experimental discovery of Weyl materials is that their gaplessness implies that in principle they should possess any type of a *bulk* response that exists in a conventional metal with the same symmetry. Thus it appears to be challenging to try to find “new” bulk effects in Weyl semimetals; more often than not one discovers unusual in some sense behavior in the known phenomena. This paper is devoted to the study of well-known phenomenon of natural optical activity in the context of noncentrosymmetric time-reversal invariant semimetals in general, and Weyl semimetals in particular.

The observation of the previous paragraph is not as pessimistic as it may sound. First of all, the *surface* of Weyl materials is indeed unique in that it hosts Fermi arc surface states, [3] not seen in conventional two-dimensional materials. This fact has been utilized to confirm the Weyl nature of a number of materials already [4], [5], [6], and the list is rapidly growing. Second, the presence of the so-called chiral anomaly (for a review with emphasis on its condensed matter aspects, as well as historical references see Ref. [7]) leads to a number of detectable peculiarities in well-known bulk responses. For instance, the *negative* classical longitudinal magnetoresistance [8] is an example of a situation where a Weyl semimetal can be distinguished from a conventional metal using the *sign* of the response. Such negative magnetoresistance was reported in a few works by now. [9], [10], [11], [12], [13],

[14], [15] At the same time, and a bit in the spirit of the previous paragraph, this phenomenon is a property of a single partially filled three-dimensional Landau level, and at strong magnetic fields can be expected in conventional metals [16]. Thus the strong message of Ref. [8] is that the large negative longitudinal magnetoresistance can exist in Weyl semimetals in non-quantizing magnetic fields. There are more examples of Weyl semimetals’ sensitivity to magnetic fields, which manifests itself in the strong anisotropy of magneto-conductivity [17], or in the appearance of chiral-anomaly-related non-local voltage response in thin films of these materials [18]. Further, the linear band touchings appropriate for Weyl semimetals can lead to unusual behavior in optical conductivity at low doping [19], [20] $\sigma(\omega) \propto \max(\omega, T)$. Experimental observation of this behavior was claimed in Ref. [21].

Motivation for this work comes from trying to understand peculiarities of the electrodynamics of Weyl semimetals. Their electromagnetic response has attracted considerable attention in the literature.

II. ELECTRODYNAMICS OF WEYL SEMIMETALS

It has been proposed [22], [23], [24], [25] that the distinct feature of electrodynamics of Weyl semimetals is the existence of the so-called axion term [26] in the electromagnetic action

$$S[A] = \frac{e^2}{32\pi^2} \int d^4x \theta(\mathbf{r}, t) \epsilon^{\mu\nu\alpha\beta} F_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta}, \quad (1)$$

which upon integration by parts is turned into the 3D Chern-Simons action: [27]

$$S[A] = -\frac{e^2}{8\pi^2} \int d^4x \epsilon^{\mu\nu\alpha\beta} \partial_\mu \theta A_\nu \partial_\alpha A_\beta. \quad (2)$$

The physical content of this action is revealed if the corresponding current is calculated, the spatial part of which becomes

$$\mathbf{j} = \frac{e^2}{4\pi^2} \partial_t \theta \times \mathbf{E} + \frac{e^2}{4\pi^2} \partial_t \theta \mathbf{B}. \quad (3)$$

The first term on the right hand side of Eq. (3) corresponds to the anomalous Hall effect, [22], [23], [28] which is natural, since for time-independent θ , action (1) breaks the time reversal symmetry. This part of the current can be rewritten using a bulk conductivity tensor given by $\sigma_{ab} = -\epsilon_{abc} \partial_{r_c} \theta$. The last form is appropriate for general magneto-optically active metals [29] (*e.g.* itinerant ferromagnets), and is by no means specific to the case of Weyl semimetals. The implications for the electromagnetic wave propagation through Weyl semimetals with anomalous Hall effect were considered in Ref. [30].

In what follows we consider time-reversal invariant systems, which do not show Hall response.

The second term on the right hand side of Eq. (3) appears more exotic, as it describes a current flowing in response to a magnetic field, along the latter. Since current and magnetic field are polar and axial vectors, respectively, a linear relationship between them is possible only in a medium that lacks an inversion center, and indeed, a space-independent θ would break parity in action (1). In literature, the situation in which $\mathbf{j} \propto \mathbf{B}$ is referred to as the ‘‘chiral magnetic effect’’ (CME). Early works [22], [24], [25] claimed that a current proportional to the magnetic field exists in equilibrium in noncentrosymmetric Weyl semimetals. That this ground state current is in fact exactly zero was shown on general grounds in Ref. [31], and numerically confirmed for a specific model in Ref. [32]. Finally, in Ref. [33], using a specific layered model of a Weyl semimetal with broken inversion and time reversal symmetries, it was noticed that one obtains different results for the current flowing along the magnetic field depending on whether the response is considered in the static or dynamic limit: There is no current in response to a strictly static, slightly non-uniform field (static limit), but there is indeed a current $\mathbf{j} \propto \mathbf{B}$ in response to uniform, but slowly oscillating \mathbf{B} (dynamic limit). The action of Eq. (1) (or equivalent to it Eq. (2)) fails to distinguish between these limits. It was concluded in Ref. [33] that the proper response should be sought at a given frequency and wave vector,

$$\mathbf{j}(\omega, \mathbf{q}) = \eta(\omega, \mathbf{q})\mathbf{B}, \quad (4)$$

and the response coefficient $\eta(\omega, \mathbf{q})$ is non-analytic:

$$\lim_{\mathbf{q} \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\omega \rightarrow 0} \eta(\omega, \mathbf{q}) = 0, \quad \lim_{\omega \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\mathbf{q} \rightarrow 0} \eta(\omega, \mathbf{q}) \neq 0. \quad (5)$$

However, there is one more conclusion one can make: At finite frequencies the solenoidal part of the electric field and magnetic field are related by the Faraday’s law, which in Fourier components gives $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{q} \times \mathbf{E}/\omega$ (the speed of light $c = 1$), and it is a matter of convention whether to consider electric current as a response to the magnetic, or to the electric field. The general form of the conductivity tensor that would yield CME (the second term on the right hand side of Eq. (3)) as a part of total current response to the electric field for $\partial_t \theta = \text{const} \equiv -C$ is

$$\sigma_{ab}(\omega, \mathbf{q}) = \sigma_{ab}(\omega) + \lambda_{abc}(\omega)q_c \quad (6)$$

with

$$\lambda_{abc}(\omega) = C \frac{e^2}{4\pi^2\omega} \epsilon_{abc}, \quad (7)$$

where ϵ_{abc} is the antisymmetric Levi-Civita tensor. The form of the conductivity tensor (6) is well known in the literature [29], and describes natural optical activity in noncentrosymmetric media. Such media, also called gyrotropic, are characterized by different refraction indices for the two circular polarizations of electromagnetic waves. We note in passing that noncentrosymmetry is a necessary, but not sufficient condition for natural optical activity/gyrotropy. [34]

To summarize, the two equivalent forms of action, Eqs. (1) and (2), contain two very well known physical phenomena: anomalous Hall effect, and natural optical activity. This fact is definitely realized by the community by now. (See Refs. [35], [36], [37] regarding the natural optical activity part.)

III. NONLOCAL ELECTRODYNAMICS OF NONUNIFORM HELICAL METALS

In a translationally invariant system, the theory of tensor λ_{abc} from Eq. (6) was built in Ref. [38]. It was shown that the natural activity of a metal at the semiclassical level stems from the dependence of periodic parts of Bloch functions on quasimomentum.

To set the notation, we will denote the \mathbf{p} -space Hamiltonian, the energy spectrum of the crystal, and the periodic parts of the corresponding Bloch wave functions in the absence of external fields with $\hbar_{\mathbf{p}}$, $\epsilon_{n\mathbf{p}}$, and $|u_{n\mathbf{p}}\rangle$, respectively. The gradient in the quasimomentum \mathbf{p} -space is denoted with $\partial_{\mathbf{p}}$, and the derivative with respect to the a^{th} component of \mathbf{p} with ∂_a . The operator of gradient in real space is denoted with $\partial_{\mathbf{r}}$. For brevity, we set $\hbar = c = 1$ throughout the paper.

At the semiclassical level, the two objects central for the discussion are the Berry curvature of band n , $\Omega_{n\mathbf{p}}$,

$$\Omega_{n\mathbf{p}} = i\langle \partial_{\mathbf{p}} u_{n\mathbf{p}} | \times | \partial_{\mathbf{p}} u_{n\mathbf{p}} \rangle; \quad (8)$$

and the orbital magnetic moment of quasiparticles, $\mathbf{m}_{n\mathbf{p}}$,

$$\mathbf{m}_{n\mathbf{p}} = \frac{ie}{2} \langle \partial_{\mathbf{p}} u_{n\mathbf{p}} | \times (\hbar_{\mathbf{p}} - \epsilon_{n\mathbf{p}}) | \partial_{\mathbf{p}} u_{n\mathbf{p}} \rangle, \quad (9)$$

where $e < 0$ is the electron charge, and, again, $\hbar = c = 1$.

In terms of the aforementioned quantities, tensor λ_{abc} is given by [38]

$$\lambda_{abc} = -\frac{e^2}{\omega} \sum_n \int (d\mathbf{p}) \left(\epsilon_{n\mathbf{p}} (\partial_{\mathbf{p}} f_{n\mathbf{p}} \cdot \Omega_{n\mathbf{p}}) \epsilon_{abc} + \frac{1}{e} m_{nd} \partial_a f_{n\mathbf{p}} \epsilon_{dbc} + \frac{1}{e} m_{nd} \partial_b f_{n\mathbf{p}} \epsilon_{adc} \right). \quad (10)$$

To generalize the expression for the non-local conductivity tensor to the nonuniform case, it is convenient to switch to the real space. When tensor λ_{abc} is space-dependent, the correct form of the conductivity tensor is known [39] to be

$$\sigma_{ab}(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = \sigma_{ab}^0(\mathbf{r}, \omega) - \frac{i}{2} \partial_{r_c} \lambda_{abc}(\mathbf{r}, \omega) - i \lambda_{abc}(\mathbf{r}, \omega) \partial_{r_c}. \quad (11)$$

In this expression σ_{ab}^0 is a symmetric tensor, while the two other contributions are anti-symmetric with respect to exchanging a and b indices.

While the general form (11) of the conductivity tensor is well known in the literature [39], examples of its microscopic derivation are scarce. We have derived a general expression for tensor λ_{abc} for an arbitrary nonuniform system with slowly varying parameters - the limit in which Eq. (11) holds anyway.

The corresponding expression is given in terms of the exact Green’s function of a system in Wigner’s representation, $G(\mathbf{r}, \omega)$:

$$G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{p}) = \int d\rho G(\mathbf{r} + \rho/2, \mathbf{r} - \rho/2) e^{-i\mathbf{p}\rho}, \quad (12)$$

where $G(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)$ can represent any single-particle Green’s function of the system.

The final result is

$$\lambda_{abc}(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = \frac{e^2}{\hbar^2 c} \lim_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow 0} i \partial_{\mathbf{k}_c} \frac{1}{V} \sum_{\mathbf{p}} \int \frac{d\varepsilon}{4\pi i} \text{Tr} \partial_{\mathbf{p}_a} h_0(\mathbf{p}) \left[G_R(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{p}_+; \varepsilon_+) \partial_{\mathbf{p}_b} h_0(\mathbf{p}) G_K(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{p}_-; \varepsilon_-) + G_K(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{p}_+; \varepsilon_+) \partial_{\mathbf{p}_b} h_0(\mathbf{p}) G_A(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{p}_-; \varepsilon_-) \right] \quad (13)$$

In this expression $G_{R,A,K}$ are the standard retarded, advanced, and Keldysh Green's functions of the system, $\mathbf{p}_{\pm} = \mathbf{p} \pm \mathbf{k}/2$, $\varepsilon_{\pm} = \varepsilon \pm \omega/2$, and $\partial_{\mathbf{p}} h_0(\mathbf{p})$ represent the velocity vortex of the uniform system.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work we extend the understanding of natural optical activity in semimetals in the following ways: *i*) We obtain an expression for tensor λ_{abc} that determines the spatial dispersion of conductivity, Eq. (6), which is valid for arbitrary band structures. In general, we find that there are many conflicting results regarding this tensor in the literature. In particular, our results differ from those of Refs. [40], [35], [36], [37], but have been subsequently confirmed in Ref. [41] *ii*) We have generalized the treatment to nonuniform system, where we obtained a fully microscopic result in line with Onsager symmetry relations for response coefficients.

The aforementioned advances can be used to describe general helical metals with natural optical activity, consider electromagnetic wave behavior at sample boundaries, and describe quantum transport in samples of finite dimensions.

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